

Can the ‘Synodal Way’ overcome the Scourge of Clericalism in the Church?

Thomas Karimundackal, SJ

Abstract

Clericalism distorts the face of the Church as it is a perversion of Christian principles. Pope Francis has been denouncing clericalism throughout his pontificate. In the context of the forthcoming synod on synodality, Pope Francis offers a ‘synodal way’ to fight against clericalism prevailing in the Church. He believes that the mission fuelled by communion and participation of all the members of the Church can break through the culture of clerical privilege dominant in the Church. This paper focuses on Pope Francis’ critique of clericalism and his dream of a synodal church.

Introduction

Clericalism is one of the crucial challenges that the Church faces today, and it distorts the face of the Church. No one can say that the ministerial hierarchy in the Church is bad as it is meant to serve others.¹ Even from early Christianity, we find this hierarchy of order where the ministers of different orders served the Church and proclaimed the Lord’s message by the guidelines of competent authority. However, in the course of time, it took a different turn and hampered the spread and sustenance of Christian principles in the Church. If we can call clericalism an arbitrary exercise of power, this arbitrariness ruptures the relationship between the laity and clergy.

No doubt, clericalism is a perversion of Christian principles. As Nelson explains, clericalism in the Catholic Church is considered “the situation in which the clergy are seen as the church, as ‘normative of godliness or holiness, and where ‘lay people are denied an equal share in the decision-making processes of the

¹ Popes from the time of St. Gregory the Great have taken the title *servus servorum Dei*, “servant of the servants of God.”

church, equal access to resources of theology, spirituality and training’ and as seen by the clergy as ‘being passive, needing teaching, unspiritual, untheological, unresponsive and ultimately irresponsible, unable to be trusted with the things that matter - the holy mysteries.’”² Thus, clericalism in the Catholic Church promotes an idea that only ordained clergy, such as priests and bishops, have only true authority to make decisions, that all should accept their decisions, and that ^{they are very} special and superior to lay faithful in all matters.³ Unfortunately, the theology of the priesthood, such as “alter Christus” and “persona Christi” had supported the isolation of clerics into a special class, different from the lay people.⁴ It created a distorted attitude toward clergy and an assumption of their spiritual and moral superiority.⁵

As Pope Francis notes, although the priesthood is considered ‘hierarchical,’ this function is not meant to be superior to the others but is totally ordered to the Holiness of Christ’s Members.⁶ Therefore, the Pope has been denouncing clericalism throughout his pontificate. He is constantly reminding us that clericalism is one of the major problems of the Church today. He believes that there is a great need for synodality to fight against the evil of clericalism prevailing in the Church.⁷ According to him, the Council of Jerusalem (50 CE) to the Second Vatican Council (1962-65) have always been moments to listen to different perspectives and find a common path.⁸ Therefore, he foresees that the synod on synodality would invite everyone to walk together and listen to one another for a synodal Church, a Church without a clerical mentality.

² Nelson, John. “An Abuse of Power: Bishops and Clericalism,” in *Modern Believing*, vol. 36, no. 2, Apr. 1995, 46.

³ Plante, Thomas G. “Clericalism Contributes to Religious, Spiritual, and Behavioural Struggles among Catholic Priests.,” in *Religions*, vol. 11, no. 5, May 2020, 2.

⁴ Richard Gaillardetz says, “such a theology presumes a very privatized notion of priestly vocation, moving too easily from a sense of God’s call to the individual’s acceptance of that call, and overlooking entirely the necessary mediating role of the church as the context in which that call is discerned, assessed, and cultivated.” Richard R. Gaillardetz, “A Church in Crisis: How Did We Get Here? How Do We Move Forward?” in *Worship*, vol. 93, July 2019, 210.

⁵ <https://aleteia.org/2018/08/23/what-is-clericalism/> (accessed on 10 January 2023).

⁶ Pope Francis, *Post Synodal Apostolic Exhortation: Querida Amazonia* (2 February 2020), 87-88.

⁷ Pope on Synod: The participation of everyone, guided by the Holy Spirit, 09 October 2021 <https://www.vaticannews.va/en/pope/news/2021-10/pope-francis-discourse-moment-reflection-eve-inauguration-synod.html>, n.p. (accessed on 10 January 2023).

⁸ *Ibid.*

Pope Francis on Clericalism

Pope Francis, while addressing the Synod Fathers at the opening of Synod 2018 on Young People, the Faith, and Vocational Discernment has defined clericalism as,

It (clericalism) arises from an elitist and exclusivist vision of vocation that interprets the ministry received as a power to be exercised rather than as a free and generous service to be given. This leads us to believe that we belong to a group that has all the answers and no longer needs to listen or learn anything. Clericalism is a perversion and is the root of many evils in the Church: we must humbly ask forgiveness for this and above all create the conditions so that it is not repeated.⁹

Pope Francis, during his meeting with the bishops of Chile, in 2018, mentioned the following about clericalism:¹⁰

- Clericalism emerges due to the lack of consciousness of belonging to God's faithful people as servants, not masters.
- Clericalism fails to realize that the mission belongs to the entire Church, not the individual priest or bishop.
- Clericalism, far from giving impetus to various contributions and proposals, gradually extinguishes the prophetic flame to which the entire Church is called to bear witness.
- Clericalism forgets that the Church's visibility and sacramentality belong to all the faithful people of God (LG 9-14), not only to the few chosen and enlightened.

Pope Francis' voice becomes very harsh when he speaks about clericalism: "Let us be clear about this. The laypersons are not our peons, or our employees. They don't have to parrot back whatever we say."¹¹ Therefore, he warns against the

⁹ <https://zenit.org/2018/10/03/pope-francis-address-to-the-synod-fathers-at-opening-of-synod2018-on-young-people-the-faith-and-vocational-discernment/> (accessed on 10 January 2023).

¹⁰ Greeting of the Holy Father on the occasion of his meeting with the bishops of Chile, 16 January 2018, https://www.vatican.va/content/francesco/en/speeches/2018/January/documents/papa-francesco_20180116_cile-santiago-vescovi.html (accessed on 15 January 2023).

¹¹ Ibid.

temptation to manipulate the laity. Rather, he urges clerics to empower them. He reminded the bishops of Chile, “Lay people are part of the faithful Holy People of God and thus are the protagonists of the Church and of the world; we [priests] are called to serve them, not to be served by them.”¹² However, Pope Francis also warns against the ‘clericalization of the laity’ saying that their aspiration should not be part of the “Sanhedrin” that gathers around the parish priest, but to be part of the “school of holiness and to be an evangelizer.”¹³ So according to the Pope, the ‘clericalization’ of the laity is equally bad as the ‘clericalism’ of the clergy.

Recalling his letter to Cardinal Marc Ouellet, President of the Pontifical Commission for Latin America, on 21 March 2016, Pope Francis says that “clericalism, far from giving impetus to various contributions and proposals, gradually extinguishes the prophetic flame to which the entire Church is called to bear witness. Clericalism forgets that the Church’s visibility and sacramentality belong to all the faithful people of God (cf. *LG*, 9-14), not only to the few chosen and enlightened”.¹⁴ He further emphasises that “clericalism nullifies the character of Christians. It tends to diminish and undervalue the baptismal grace that the Holy Spirit has placed in the heart of our people.”¹⁵

In an impassioned letter addressed to the whole ‘People of God,’ quoting Pope Benedict XVI’s words during the Way of the Cross on Good Friday 2005, Pope Francis shows the gravity of the problems of clericalism: “How much filth there is in the Church, and even among those who, in the priesthood, ought to belong entirely to [Christ]! How much pride, how much self-complacency!”¹⁶ He reasons that clericalism, whether fostered by priests or lay persons, leads to an excision in the ecclesial body that supports and helps to perpetuate many of the evils we are condemning today.¹⁷

¹² Letter to Cardinal Marc Ouellet, President of the Pontifical Commission for Latin America (19 March 2016), https://www.vatican.va/content/francesco/en/letters/2016/documents/papa-francesco_20160319_pont-comm-america-latina.html (accessed on 15 January 2023).

¹³ *Ibid.*

¹⁴ *Ibid.*

¹⁵ Letter to Cardinal Marc Ouellet (accessed on 15 January 2023).

¹⁶ Letter of His Holiness Pope Francis to the People of God https://www.vatican.va/content/francesco/en/letters/2018/documents/papa-francesco_20180820_lettera-popolo-didio.html (accessed on 15 January 2023).

¹⁷ *Ibid.*

Therefore, Pope Francis rightly calls it a disease that has infected the Church. He substantiates it from his own experience: “I have seen it in the course of my pastoral visits in my own diocese and elsewhere in my meetings and personal conversations with priests; many shared with me their anger at what happened and their disturbance that for all their hard work, they have to face the damage that was done, the suspicion and uncertainty to which it has given rise, and the doubts, fears, and disheartenment felt by more than a few.”¹⁸

In his Homily in Casa Santa Marta in 2016, Pope Francis said, “There is that Spirit of Clericalism in the Church ... Clerics feel superior; Clerics distance themselves from the People. Clerics always say: ‘this should be done like this, like this, like this, and you – go away!’ It happens when the cleric doesn’t have time to listen to those who are suffering, the poor, the sick, and the imprisoned: the evil of clericalism is a awful thing.”¹⁹ He further adds that “clericalism in the Church is a terrible evil with ancient roots and always victimizes “poor and humble people.”²⁰

During the Chrism Mass on 18 April 2019, the Pope said, “clericalism takes root when you seek comfort instead of the people. Therefore, clergy must identify with ordinary people, be ready to serve, and in doing so will find their priesthood come alive. Priests are not ‘distributors of bottled oil’ but anoint through dirtying their hands in touching the wounds, the sins and the worries of the people, and by giving of themselves generously to the people.”²¹ So the Pope asks priests to learn how to “anoint,” to anoint though “dirtying our hands in touching the wounds, the sins and the worries of the people,” and by giving of themselves generously to the people rather than considering ourselves “distributors of bottled oil.” The Pope continued: “Here, I believe, was the

¹⁸ Letter of His Holiness Pope Francis to Priests on the 160th Anniversary of the Death of the Holy Curé of Ars, St John Vianney, https://www.vatican.va/content/francesco/en/letters/2019/documents/papa-francesco_20190804lettera-presbiteri.html (accessed on 15 January 2023).

¹⁹ Pope Francis, *People discarded*, Morning Meditation in the Chapel of the Domus Sanctae Marthae, Tuesday, 13 December 2016 https://www.vatican.va/content/francesco/en/cotidie/2016/documents/papa-francesco-cotidie_20161213_people-discarded.html (accessed on 15 January 2023).

²⁰ *Ibid.*

²¹ *The Tablet*, <https://www.thetablet.co.uk/news/11607/pope-to-priests-clericalism-takes-root-when-you-seek-comfort-instead-of-the-people>, 18 April 2019 (accessed on 14 January 2023).

beginning of clericalism: in this desire to be assured of a meal and personal comfort without any concern for the people.”²² So, according to Pope Francis, the roots of clericalism are planted with a desire to place personal comfort ahead of service. He says it pains him to see clergy driving around in flashy cars and young clerics turn into “little monsters” and “rigid and worldly.”²³

During the summit on clerical sexual abuse (2019), Pope Francis identifies clericalism as one of the major sources of terrible clergy abuse scandals.²⁴ According to him, “the clerical culture looks to protect the institution even at the expense of individuals who have been harmed.”²⁵ He further says that “no” to abuse is to say an emphatic “no” to all forms of clericalism²⁶ because he thinks that clericalism and abuse of power are at the heart of the clerical sexual abuse crisis.²⁷

Undoubtedly, the formation in the seminary plays a vital role in creating the clerical attitude. As Doyle argues, “clerics are taught from the seminary onward that celibacy makes them superior to the non-celibate because it requires a higher degree of internal strength and dedication which is given to the elect by God.”²⁸ In this context, we must pay attention to the words of Pope Francis to the seminarians. In his address to the seminarians of the Diocese of Agrigento, Saturday, 24 November 2018, Pope Francis tells the young Seminarians that they must remember where they came from because “when we forget this, we fall into clericalism.”²⁹ And he continues: “Please do not forget your Mother, Father, Grandmother, Grandfather, Village, Poverty, and the

²² Ibid.

²³ Ibid.

²⁴ <https://www.usatoday.com/story/news/world/2019/02/19/vatican-sex-abuse-summit-pope-francis-hosts-summit-abuse-crisis/2905068002/> (accessed on 14 January 2023).

²⁵ Ibid.

²⁶ Letter of His Holiness Pope Francis to the People of God (accessed on 14 January 2023).

²⁷ The Tablet, <https://www.thetablet.co.uk/news/11607/pope-to-priests-clericalism-takes-root-when-you-seek-comfort-instead-of-the-people>, 18 April 2019 (accessed on 14 January 2023).

²⁸ Doyle, Thomas P. “Roman Catholic Clericalism, Religious Duress, and Clergy Sexual Abuse,” in *Pastoral Psychology*, vol. 51, no. 3, Jan. 2003, 189–231.

²⁹ Address of His Holiness Pope Francis to Seminarians of the Diocese of Agrigento, Consistory Hall, Saturday, 24 November 2018, https://www.vatican.va/content/francesco/en/speeches/2018/november/documents/papafrancesco_20181124_seminaristi-agrigento.html (accessed on 14 January 2023).

Difficulties of Families: do not forget them ... the Lord has taken you from there, from the people of God because with this, with this memory, you will know how to speak to the people of God, how to serve the People of God.”³⁰ He says that he is concerned about the formation of seminarians, that they be pastors at the service of the People of God, who will denounce every form of clericalism: “Seminaries must stress that future priests be capable of serving God’s holy and faithful people, acknowledging the diversity of cultures and renouncing the temptation to any form of clericalism. ... Their mission is carried out in fraternal unity with the whole People of God. Side by side, supporting and encouraging the laity in a climate of discernment and synodality, two of the essential features of the priest of tomorrow. Let us say no to clericalism and ideal worlds that are only part of our thinking, but touch the life of no one.”³¹

The Synodal Way to overcome the Scourge of Clericalism

The Second Vatican Council (*LG* 32-33) reinvigorated the sense that all the baptised, both the hierarchy and the laity, are called to be active participants in the saving mission of the Church. We all know that there cannot be a Church without the laity: *Lumen Gentium* articulates it very clearly: “By reason of their special vocation, it belongs to the laity to seek the kingdom of God by engaging in temporal affairs and directing them according to God’s will. They live in the world, that is, they are engaged in each and every work and business of the earth and in the ordinary circumstances of social and family life which, as it were, constitute their very existence” (*LG* 31). In the ceremony to commemorate the 50th anniversary of the institution of the Synod of Bishops in October 2015, Pope Francis declared that “every one of the baptised should feel involved in the ecclesial and social change that we so greatly need. This change calls for a personal and communal conversion that makes us see things as the Lord does.”³² Pope Francis is renewing this struggle with the clericalist values that have still not disappeared.

As we know, in April 2021, Pope Francis initiated a synodal journey of the whole People of God, to begin in October 2021 in each local Church and

³⁰ Ibid.

³¹ Pope’s address to the Bishops in Santiago Cathedral on 16 January 2018. https://www.vatican.va/content/francesco/en/speeches/2018/january/documents/papa-francesco_20180116_cile-santiago-vescovi.html (accessed on 14 January 2023).

³² For a Synodal Church: Communion, Participation, and Mission. *Vademecum* for the Synod on Synodality, 07.09.2021, <https://press.vatican.va/content/salastampa/en/bollettino/pubblico/2021/09/07/210907b.html> (accessed on 14 January 2023).

culminating in October 2023 in the Assembly of the Synod of Bishops, to reflect upon the theme “For a Synodal Church: Communion, Participation, and Mission.” He envisions it as an opportunity “to overcome the scourge of clericalism.”³³ He envisages it as a journeying together to unite the whole People of God “more deeply with one another as the People of God.”³⁴ He foresees that it would enable “the entire People of God to walk forward together, listening to the Holy Spirit and the Word of God, to participate in the mission of the Church in the communion that Christ establishes between us.”³⁵ It seeks “to make pastoral decisions that reflect the will of God as closely as possible, grounding them in the living voice of the People of God.”³⁶ He believes that it will “renew our mentalities and our ecclesial structures in order to live out God’s call for the Church amid the present signs of the times.”³⁷ He thinks that it would “inspire people to dream about the Church we are called to be, to make people’s hopes flourish, to stimulate trust, to bind up wounds, to weave new and deeper relationships, to learn from one another, to build bridges, to enlighten minds, warm hearts, and restore strength to our hands for our common mission.”³⁸ The unfolding of the ‘Synodal Process’ that Pope Francis envisions involves listening, discernment, and participation regardless of location, language, education, socio-economic status, ability/disability, material resources, and cultural awareness to celebrate and embrace the diversity within local communities; it makes every effort to involve those who feel excluded or marginalized; it encourages partnership based on the model of a co-responsible Church; it respects the rights, dignity, and opinion of everyone; it ensures transparency, dialogue, and openness to conversion and changes leaving behind prejudices and stereotypes. According to Pope Francis, if listening is the method of the Synodal Process, and discerning is the aim, then participation is the path.³⁹

³³ For a Synodal Church: Communion, Participation, and Mission. *Vademecum for the Synod on Synodality*, 07.09.2021, <https://press.vatican.va/content/salastampa/en/bollettino/pubblico/2021/09/07210907b.html> (accessed on 14 January 2023).

³⁴ Ibid.

³⁵ Ibid.

³⁶ Ibid.

³⁷ Ibid.

³⁸ Ibid.

³⁹ Ibid.

Conclusion

Pope Francis offers a synodal spirit to fight against clericalism by listening to the *sensus fidelium*. A mission fuelled by communion and participation of all the members of the Church can break through the culture of clerical privilege prevailing in the Church. We cannot wipe out clericalism in a single day, but it is possible to make it happen slowly if attune to the synodal process initiated by the Pope. We are aware that clerical culture has rooted deep in the functioning of the Church especially when it comes to the institutional matter. If we are really intent on breaking up the clerical sedimentation that exists in our Church, listening to the laity by bishops and all clergy, while necessary, is not sufficient, but earnest efforts of collaboration in Church administration and leadership at all levels with the laity are obligatory. The path of synodality would definitely make the life of the Church more vibrant and participative, grounding in the living voice of the People of God, where no clergy with clerical mentality but clergy at the service of the 'People of God.'

Thomas Karimundackal teaches Biblical Theology and Biblical Languages at the Faculty of Theology, Jnana Deepa (JD), Pontifical Athenaeum of Philosophy and Theology, Pune, and currently serves as the Head of the Department of Scripture Studies, and the Chairperson of the Doctoral Programme in Theology at JD. He is the editor of *Jnanadeepa: Pune Journal of Religious Studies*, *AUC: Asian Journal of Religious Studies*, and *Christ College Pune Research Series* (CCPRS). He has authored/edited 12 books and published nearly 100 research articles in various national and international journals and periodicals. E-Mail: thomas.karimundackal@jdv.edu.in